

On the taxonomy of *Salagena tessellata* Distant, 1897 with description of a new genus and three new species (Lepidoptera, Cossioidea, Metarbelidae)

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Abstract

A new metarbelid genus, *Hermanstaudeilla* **gen. n.** is described, delimited from *Salagena* Walker, 1865, with its type species *Salagena tessellata* Distant, 1897. Three new species, *H. hillwoodi* **sp. n.** (type locality: Zambia, Hillwood Farm), *H. felixtarasenkoi* **sp. n.** (type locality: Tanzania, Ushongo Beach), *H. hackeri* **sp. n.** (type locality: Ethiopia, Nechisar National Park) are described from eastern and southern Africa. Adults, genitalia and distribution of all taxa are illustrated in 18 colour figures.

Keywords

Biodiversity, fauna, new genus, new species, systematics, southern Africa, taxonomy

Introduction

The genus *Salagena* Walker, 1865 (Lepidoptera, Cossioidea, Metarbelidae) was established to solely include *S. transversa* Walker, 1865, described from Sierra Leone (Walker 1865) (Figs 1–2, 11). According to De Prins and De Prins (2025), the genus comprises 30 species, widely distributed in Africa and in the southern regions of the Arabian Peninsula. The most widespread and widely recognised species is *Salagena tesselata* Distant, 1897, described from South Africa “Transvaal, Pretoria” (Distant 1897). This species is fairly common in South Africa, and it is even included in several Field Guides published recently (Picker et al. 2019; Staude et al. 2023). It is one of the few African species of Metarbelidae with known trophic links. Platt (1921: 88) indicated *Pyrus communis* (Rosaceae) as the food plant. *Salagena tesselata* is reported from various regions of the Republic of South Africa (Gauteng, KwaZulu Natal, Limpopo), Namibia (Zambezi Region), Eswatini, Tanzania and Kenya (Distant 1897; Staude et al. 2023; Mey 2024; De Prins and De Prins 2025). Examination of the male genitalia of *S. transversa* and *S. tesselata* revealed noticeable morphological differences, indicating that these two species are not congeneric and that a new genus should be established for *S. tesselata*. Furthermore, three additional species from northwestern Zambia, Ethiopia, and Tanzania were identified as morphologically related to *S. tesselata*; these species are described herein as new to science.

Materials and methods

The images of adults were taken by a Canon EOS 70D and a Canon EOS 600D cameras using a light box. The genitalia slides were examined under a Zeiss Stemi 2000 C and an Olympus SZX16 microscopes and imaged with an Olympus DP74 and a Canon EOS 70D cameras. The photos were edited and the illustration plates were created in Adobe Photoshop software. The distribution map was made using an open-source software (<https://www.simplemappr.net/>). The morphological terminology used in the description follows Kristensen (2003).

Abbreviations of depositories:

ANHRT – African Natural History Research Trust, Leominster, UK;

CGM – research collection of Günter Müller, Freising, Germany;

NHMUK – Natural History Museum, London, UK;

RYB – Collection of Roman Yakovlev, Barnaul, Russia;

ZISP – Zoological Institute, St.-Petersburg, Russia.

Results

Description of the new genus

Hermannstaudeilla gen. n.

<https://zoobank.org/535D110D-D75B-42CE-A402-FAF5BC888671>

Type species *Salagena tessellata* Distant, 1897 (Figs 3–6, 12, 16) (designated here).

Description. Male. Moths relatively small, with forewing length 8–13 mm. Antenna short (2.5 times shorter than forewing), bipectinate, rami 2–2.5 times longer than flagellum diameter. Apex of abdomen with cluster of long, piliform scales. Forewing ground colour and veins pale cream with areas between veins filled in with fine blackish transverse strokes forming specific pattern over entire forewing area, alternated by sparse orange-yellow transverse strokes in isolated, pale sections of forewing; fringe mottled. Hindwing pale cream to pale orange, with reduced or completely absent pattern; fringe paler than ground colour, unicolorous.

Male genitalia. Uncus bilobate with deep medial incision, lobes of uncus diverging. Gnathos arms clearly divided into two sections: proximal section thick, short, distal section very thin, long, thread-like; arms conjoined medially, forming a variably long, narrow projection. Valve short, basally broad, gradually tapering from base to apex, costal margin sclerotized basally and membranous distally, apex broadly rounded; sacculus very narrow, heavily sclerotized, shorter than half length of valve, bearing short and narrow distal fold. Juxta tightly connected to phallus, protruding together with phallus from genital capsule, shield-like. Saccus very short and narrow, semicircular. Phallus very short (shorter than half length of valve), thin or relatively thick, straight or slightly curved; vesica aperture in dorso-apical position, about half the length of phallus, vesica short, without cornuti.

Female. In habitus similar to male but antenna rami significantly shorter (only 1.5 times longer than flagellum diameter).

Female genitalia. Papilla analis short, semicircular, sparsely setose; posterior apophysis ca. 20% shorter than anterior apophysis; posterior apophysis with wide basal part; ostium bursae oval; antrum membranous, short funnel-like; ductus bursae membranous, gradually dilated anteriorly; bursa copulatrix bag-shaped, membranous, without signa.

Diagnosis. Externally, the species of the new genus are reminiscent of the West African type species of the genus *Salagena*, *S. transversa*: however, distinguished in the following male genital features:

- shape of the deeply split bilobed uncus (in *S. transversa* the uncus is long, apically dilated with apex shallowly notched postero-medially);
- the presence of dilated extensions in the proximal section of the gnathos arms (in *S. transversa* the proximal section of the gnathos arms is equally thick, without dilated extensions);

- the gradually tapered, rounded-triangular valve (in *S. transversa*, the valve is very short, rounded).

Etymology. The new genus is named after Hermann S. Staude (Hoekwil, South Africa), a renowned South-African lepidopterologist.

Taxon content. The genus comprises four species: *Hermannstaudeilla tessellata* (Distant, 1897) **comb. n.**, *H. felixtarasenkoi* **sp. n.**, *H. hackeri* **sp. n.** and *H. hillwoodi* **sp. n.**

Distribution. The representatives of the genus are distributed in southern Africa (common) and southern-central and eastern Africa (relatively rare).

Redescription of *Salagena tessellata* Distant, 1897

Hermannstaudeilla tessellata (Distant, 1897) **comb. n.**

Figs 3–6, 12, 16, 18

Material examined. Republic of South Africa. 1 female, Holotype, Transvaal, Pretoria, W.L. Distant (NHMUK, unique number: NHMUK010297703); 10 males, 1 female: South Africa, KwaZulu-Natal, Pongola, Belvedere Game Ranch, 27°31'S, 31°45'E, 430m, 22–26.ii.2018, Kovtunovich, V., Yakovlev, R. leg. (ANHRT, RYB); 2 males, Republic of South Africa, KwaZulu-Natal province, Sebaya lake, 27°23'47" S, 32°42'43" E, polydominant savanna, 20 m, 26.xi.2021, R.V. Yakovlev leg. (RYB); 9 males, Southern Africa, KwaZulu-Natal Province, Pongola Region, Belvedere Game Ranch, 400 m, 27°31'45" S 31°45'37" E, 26–29.02.2024, leg Roman & Lidiya Yakovlev (RYB); 1 male, Republic of South Africa, KwaZulu-Natal province, Cumberland national park, 29°30'33" S, 30°30'32" E, polydominant savanna, 610 m, 22.11.2021, R.V. Yakovlev leg. (RYB); 18 males, Republic of South Africa, KwaZulu-Natal province, Nduma national park, 26°54'34" S, 32°18'52" E, Acacia savanna, 70 m, 27–29.11.2021, R.V. Yakovlev leg. (RYB); 1 male, Republic of South Africa, KwaZulu-Natal province, Pangola, Belvedere Game Ranch, S 27°31' / E 31°45', 30.11–2.12.2021, R.V. Yakovlev leg. (RYB); 1 male, Republic of South Africa, Mpumalanga province, Low's Creek lodge, 25°39'58" S, 31°16'33" E, 510 m, 3–5.12.2021, R.V. Yakovlev leg. (RYB); 1 male, Republic of South Africa, KwaZulu-Natal province, Weenen nature reserve, 28°50'14" S, 29°59'48" E, 1100 m, 6–8.12.2021, R.V. Yakovlev leg. (RYB); 1 male, Same locality, 4.12.2011 (leg. P. Ustjuzhanin); 14 males, South Africa, Northern [Limpopo] province, Camp David, 475 m, 5 km S Ofcolaco, 17–24 Jan. 2002, leg. S. Murzin (CGM); 1 male, Rep. Südafrika, Ost-Transvaal, Drakensberge, Alistairs Farm bei Montrose, ca. 14 km W Nelspruit, bushveld, ca. 25°25'S 30°44'E, 900 m, LF, 28–30.i.1989, leg. Oberprieier & Nassig (CGM); 1 male, South Africa, Limpopo, Soutpansberg, 22°59' S 29°45' E, 1400 m, 2–13.ii.2013, leg. Stadie & Schintlmeister (CGM); 1 female, Südafrika, Mpumalanga, 50 km NNW Nelspruit, Umg. Hazyview, 780 m, 2–3.ii.2002 (CGM); 1 male, Südafrika, Provinz Limpopo, 8 km S Louis Trichard, Ben Lavin nature Reserve, 1000 m, 21–28.xii.2008 (CGM).

Eswatini. 1 male, Eswatini, Manzini Prov., Dombeya Wildlife, 415 m, 16–19.ii.2020, Knud Larsen (CGM).

Zimbabwe. 25 males, Zimbabwe, Masvingo Province, 20 km NW Buffalo Range, Jiri Dam, Jiri Camp Chalets, 20°56'16" S 31°23'40" E, 450 m, 16–17.ii.2025, leg. Roman Yakovlev (RYB); 3 males, Zimbabwe, Manicaland Province, 5 km W Birchenough Bridge, Mapari Rest Resort, 19°57'32" S 32°14'52" E, 550 m, 11–13.ii.2025, leg. Roman Yakovlev (RYB).

Mozambique. 17 males, Mozambique, Maputo Special Reserve, Futi Corridor (Sand Forest Woodland Mosaic) 26°32'10.1" S, 32°43'09.7" E, 23–24.ii.2018, László, G., Mulvaney, J., Smith, L. leg. (ANHRT); Mozambique, 22 males, Maputo Special Reserve, West Gate, Sand Forest/Sand Thicket, 26°30'14.2" S, 32°42'59.6" E, 9–22.ii.2018, László, G., Mulvaney, J., Smith, L. leg. (ANHRT); Same locality, 21–30.xi.2016, 3–13.xii.2016, Aristophanous, M., Cristóvão, J., László, G., Miles, W. leg.; Mozambique, 15 males, Maputo Special Reserve, Ponta Milibangalala, Dune Grassland, 26°26'58.6" S, 32°55'29.8" E, 17–21.ii.2018, László, G., Mulvaney, J., Smith, L. leg. (ANHRT); Same locality, 30.xi.–3.xii.2016, Aristophanous, M., Cristóvão, J., László, G., Miles, W. leg. (ANHRT).

Redescription. Male. Length of forewing 9–12 mm. Antenna completely yellow, frons with a group of orange scales, thorax covered with dense yellow scales, abdomen basally covered with light-yellow scales dorsally, distally covered with bright-yellow scales, apically with a cluster of long, black and yellow piliform scales. Forewing creamy, with fine, thin pattern of strokes on entire wing area with alternating black strokes (concentrated basally, postdiscally and along costal margin) and orange-yellow strokes (located as separate, isolated groups, mostly medio-basally and discally), fringe mottled (yellow between veins, orange at veins). Hindwing yellow, without pattern, fringe yellow, unicolorous.

Male genitalia. Uncus bilobed, with deep medial incision, lobes of uncus reminiscent of rabbit ears, diverging distally at acute angle. Gnathos arms clearly divided into two sections: proximal section of arm short and thick, ending in robust club-like dilation, continued abruptly in very thin and long, thread-like distal section joining medially forming a narrow and relatively long, pointed projection. Valve relatively short, triangular, medially slightly constricted, valve costa well-sclerotized basally and membranous distally, apex rounded; sacculus short and narrow, ca. half as long as valve, well-sclerotized, ventrally slightly curved, bearing a small, semicircular process shaped as small fold. Juxta fused to phallus, plate-like; saccus semicircular, very small. Phallus very short (ca. one-third the length of valve), narrow, slightly curved, vesica aperture in dorso-apical position, rather long, about half of phallus in length, vesica without cornuti.

Female. Externally similar to male, the only difference is the shorter antenna rami (1.5 times longer than flagellum in diameter).

Female genitalia. Papilla analis semicircular, membranous, weakly setose; posterior apophysis ca. two-thirds in length of anterior apophysis; posterior apophysis with wide basal section. Ostium bursae oval, poorly sclerotized; antrum membra-

nous, funnel-shaped. Ductus bursae long, narrow, membranous; bursa copulatrix bag-shaped, membranous, without signa.

Diagnosis. Compared to other species of the genus, *H. tessellata* is noticeably more bright in colour, with a well-developed orange pattern of strokes in the forewing. In the male genitalia, this species has the longest and widest lobes of uncus, the most expressed club-like dilation of the basal section of the gnathos arms, the most concave costal margin of the valve and the most elongate fold-like saccular lobe.

Distribution. Republic of South Africa (Eastern Part), Eswatini, Zimbabwe, Mozambique. The reports from Botswana (North-West), Namibia (Zambezi Region), Tanzania, and Kenya are not supported by factual material and need verification.

Descriptions of new species

Hermannstaudeilla hillwoodi sp. n.

<https://zoobank.org/56F6F887-A31C-41C5-816B-7B183725E19C>

Figs 7–8, 13, 17–18

Material examined. Holotype, male, North-West Zambia, Hillwood Farm, S 11°16.01' E 24°18.99', 1420 m, 17.ix.2009, leg. J. Lenz (RYB/ZISP, slide PP 0107).

Paratypes. 2 males, Zambia, Changwena Falls, N. Swaka F.R., Copperbelt, 1416 m, S 13°22'48" E 29°3'18", 27–28.x.2014, leg. Smith, Takano & Oram (ANHRT, individual numbers 00436062 and 00436479, slide ANHRT Pavlova & Yakovlev 2025/075); 1 male, Zambia, lake Kashiba, Mpongwe, S 13°26'55" E 27°56'40", 25–26.x.2014, leg. Smith, Takano & Oram (ANHRT, individual number 00436481); 1 male, 1 female, Zambia, 10 km sud Muyombe, 10°39'56" S 33°27'23" E, 1257 m, 23.xi.2011 (CGM); 1 female, Zambia, Central Province, Kasanka NP, S 12°54'11.4 E 30°37'43.812, 3–4 Nov. 2012, 1100 m, leg. Elk Ott & H. Sulak (CGM).

Description. Male. Length of forewing 10–11 mm. Antenna pale yellow, short (2.5 times shorter than forewing), bipectinate, rami 2 times longer than flagellum in diameter. Frons with a cluster of coal-black scales, thorax covered with black scales, tegulae and patagia covered with brown scales. Abdomen basally covered with white scales and groups of coal-black scales on dorsal surface; distally covered with light-yellow scales, apically with cluster of long black and yellow piliform scales. Forewing white, with thin, fine pattern of dense black strokes throughout wing surface and orange-yellow strokes located in small groups basally, medio-basally, and discally; fringe mottled (white between veins and dark with alternating yellow and brown scales at veins). Hindwing white with very weak pattern of sparse black scales and hardly noticeable yellow spots, fringe light-yellow, unicolorous.

Male genitalia. Uncus bilobed, V-shaped, with deep medial incision. Gnathos arms clearly divided into two sections: proximal section short and thick, ending in club-like dilation, distal portion of arm very thin and long, thread-like, ending

in short, narrowly-rounded medial projection. Valve relatively short, valve costa well-sclerotized basally and membranous distally, with distinct margin between sclerotized and membranous sections, apex broad, rounded-quadrangular. Sacculus short and narrow, shorter than half the length of valve, well-sclerotized, ventrally slightly curved, bearing a small, semicircular process shaped as short ridge. Juxta fused to phallus, small, plate-like; saccus rounded triangular, very small. Phallus very short (more than twice shorter than valve), relatively thick, slightly curved, vesica aperture in dorso-apical position, about half of phallus in length, vesica without cornuti.

Female. Externally very similar to male with antenna rami shorter (1.5 times longer than flagellum in diameter), more diffuse forewing pattern and darker yellow hindwing.

Female genitalia. Papilla analis semicircular, membranous, weakly setose; posterior apophysis ca. two-thirds in length of anterior apophysis; posterior apophysis with wide basal section. Ostium bursae oval, poorly sclerotized; antrum membranous, funnel-shaped. Ductus bursae very short, membranous; bursa copulatrix elongate sack-like, membranous, without signa.

Diagnosis. *Hermannstaudeilla hillwoodi* **sp. n.** differs from its congeners in the paler, more whitish ground colour, the more contrasting blackish strokes of the forewing and the markedly lighter hindwing colouration. In the male genitalia, this new species has a V-shaped uncus with the shortest lobes and the largest, apically widest valve compared to its congeners.

Etymology. The new species is named after the type locality, the Hillwood Farm – a unique, diverse site in north-western Zambia. Hillwood is one of the few large-scale commercial farms in the northern Mwinilunga District, where a thriving community has grown. It was founded and is still run by the Fisher family, who first arrived in the area as missionaries at the end of the nineteenth century. In addition to the livestock and arable farming, a game ranch, called Nchila Wildlife Reserve, has been established there. The three dominant habitats in the area are hygrophilous grassland (dambo), dry miombo woodland, and gallery forest (mushitu). The grasslands range from wet, peaty swamps to drier, sandy areas typical of the region's watersheds. In many areas, the miombo woodland forms a mosaic with patches of dry evergreen forest, and along the drainage lines are strips of wet, evergreen gallery forest (Bingham et al. 2025).

Distribution. Northern Zambia.

Hermannstaudeilla felixtarasenkoi **sp. n.**

<https://zoobank.org/4E9B0C1F-0C85-4478-92B0-279076A45B3A>

Figs 9, 14, 18

Material examined. Holotype, male, Tanzania, Region Tango [Tango], Ushongo Beach, 05°32.510 S 38°08.080 E, 14–15.v.2010, 1340 m, leg. J. Cave & T.A. Newton-Chance (ANHRT, slide ANHRT Pavlova & Yakovlev 2025/086). Paratype, 1 male, same locality (CGM, slide Prozorov 2025 1578).

Figures 1–10. Adults. **1.** *Salagena transversa*, Syntype, male, Sierra Leone (NHMUK, unique number: NHMUK010297706); **2.** *S. transversa*, male, N. Nigeria, Zaria, Samaru, 16.iv.1977, J.C. Demeeng (NHMUK, unique number: NHMUK010290882). Continued on next page.

Figures 1–10. Continued from previous page 3. *Hermannstaudeilla tessellata*, Holotype, female, Transvaal, Pretoria, W.L. Distant (NHMUK, unique number: NHMUK010297703); 4. *H. tessellata*, male, S. Africa Rep., Kwazulu Natal, Pongola, Belvedere G.R., S 27°31' E 31°45'; h 430 m, 22–26.02.2018, leg. R.V. Yakovlev (RYB); 5. *H. tessellata*, male, Mozambique, Maputo Special Reserve, West Gate, Sand Forest/Sand Thicket, 26°30'14.2"S, 32°42'59.6"E, 10–17.ii.2018, László, G., Mulvaney, J., Smith, L. leg. (ANHRT); 6. *H. tessellata*, female, Südafrika, Mpumalanga, 50 km NNW Nelspruit, Umg. Hazyview, 780 m, 2–3.ii.2002 (CGM); 7. *H. hillwoodi* sp. n., Holotype, male, North-West Zambia, Hillwood Farm, S 11°16.01' E 24°18.99', 1420 m, 17.ix.2009, leg. J. Lenz (RYB/ZISP); 8. *H. hillwoodi* sp. n., Paratype, female, Zambia, 10 km sud Muyombe, 10°39'56" S 33°27'23" E, 1257 m, 23.xi.2011 (CGM); 9. *H. felixtarasenkoi* sp. n., Holotype, male, Tanzania, Region Tango [Tango], Ushongo Beach, 05°32.510 S 38°08.080, 14–15.v.2010, 1340 m, leg. J. Cave & T.A. Newton-Chance (ANHRT); 10. *H. hackeri* sp. n., Holotype, male, Ethiopia / Southern, Arba Minch, Nechisar NP, 2.75 km SW headquarter, 06°00'13.6" N 37°33'23.4" E, 1170 m, 22.ii.2012, leg. H. Hacker & H.-P. Schreier (CGM, slide Prozorov 2025 1627) (CGM).

Description. Male. Length of forewing 8 mm. Antenna pale yellow, short (2.5 times shorter than forewing), bipectinate, rami 2 times longer than flagellum in diameter. Thorax covered with cream scales, tegulae and patagia covered with light-brown scales, abdomen cream, apically with cluster of long black and yellow pili-form scales. Forewing white, with thin, fine pattern of dense black strokes throughout wing surface and sparse groups of orange strokes basally, medio-basally, and discally and along costal margin; fringe mottled (white between veins and yellow at veins). Hindwing cream without pattern, fringe light-yellow, unicolorous.

Male genitalia. Uncus bilobed, with deep medial incision, lobes narrow digitiform, diverging distad. Gnathos arms clearly divided into two sections: proximal section of arm short and thick, ending in club-like dilation, distal section of arm very thin, long, thread-like, arms fused medially in a small, elongate, apically rounded plate. Valve short, triangular, costal margin almost straight, apex rounded, sacculus well-sclerotized, short (ca. half as long as ventral margin of valve) and narrow, slightly curved, with small semicircular, fold-like process. Juxta fused to phallus, small, plate-like; saccus semicircular, tiny. Phallus very short (ca. one-third the length of valve), narrow, almost straight, vesica aperture in dorso-apical position, about half the length of phallus; vesica without cornuti.

Female unknown.

Diagnosis. *Hermannstaudeilla felixtarasenkoi* sp. n. differs from other species of the genus in the weakly developed orange strokes on the forewing and in the characteristically thin lobes of the uncus.

Etymology. The new species is named after the uncle of the last author, Doctor of Technical Sciences, Honorary Professor of Tomsk State University, Felix P. Tarasenko (1932–2021). In 1967 and 1968, as a UNESCO expert, he had been a senior lecturer at the University of Dar es Salaam in Tanzania.

Distribution. Tanzania, Tanga Region.

Hermannstaudeilla hackeri sp. n.

<https://zoobank.org/9F1DA362-FA87-42A1-8A61-F0C2D7528A36>

Figs 10, 15, 18

Material examined. Holotype, male, Ethiopia / Southern, Arba Minch, Nechisar NP, 2.75 km SW headquarter, 06°00'13.6" N 37°33'23.4" E, 1170 m, 22.ii.2012, leg. H. Hacker & H.-P. Schreier (CGM, slide Prozorov 2025 1627).

Paratypes. 6 males, same locality (CGM); 4 males, Ethiopia, Oromia, Bale mountains NP, Harena Forest, 14 km S Rira, 06°38'48.1" N 39°43'55.0" E, 20.ii.2012, 1902 m, leg. H. Hacker & H.-P. Schreier (CGM).

Description. Male. Length of forewing 11–13 mm. Antenna orange, short (2.5 times shorter than forewing), bipectinate, rami 2 times longer than flagellum in diameter. Frons with a cluster of coal-black scales, thorax covered with black, orange and white scales, abdomen basally covered with light-yellow scales dorsally, with two groups of coal-black scales, abdomen distally covered with orange scales, apically with cluster of long black and white piliform scales. Forewing cream, with very dense pattern of black strokes (in some places merging into large black spots and bands) throughout entire wing surface with small, isolated groups of orange strokes medio-basally, discally, and along costal margin, fringe mottled (yellow between veins and brown at veins). Hindwing yellow without pattern, fringe yellow, mottled: white between veins and yellow at veins.

Male genitalia. Uncus bilobed, with deep medial incision, lobes of uncus reminiscent of rabbit ears, diverging distad at acute angle. Gnathos arms clearly divided into two sections: proximal section of arm short and thick, distal section very thin, long thread-like, arms fused medially without forming a plate or projection. Valve relatively long, triangular, costal margin almost straight, apex rounded, sacculus well sclerotized, short (shorter than half the length of ventral margin of valve) and narrow, slightly curved, with small semicircular fold-like process. Juxta fused to phallus, shield-like; saccus semicircular, tiny. Phallus very short (more than twice shorter than valve), relatively thick, almost straight, vesica aperture in dorso-apical position, about half of phallus in length, vesica without cornuti.

Female unknown.

Diagnosis. *Hermannstaudeilla hackeri* sp. n. displays the most contrasting forewing colouration in the genus with the most extensive blackish markings. In the male genitalia, this new species is distinguished from its congeners by its relatively long valve and the proximal part of the gnathos arm, lacking a club-shaped dilation.

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to Hermann H. Hacker, an eminent German lepidopterologist, leading authority in African Noctuoidea.

Distribution. Southern Ethiopia.

Figures 11–17. Genitalia. **11.** *S. transversa*, male, N. Nigeria (slide NHMUK014333363); **12.** *H. tessellata*, male, S. Africa Rep., Kwazulu Natal, Pongola, Belvedere G.R. (RYB, slide PP 0105); **13.** *H. hillwoodi* **sp. n.**, Holotype, male (RYB/ZISP, slide PP 0107); **14.** *H. felixtarasenkoi* **sp. n.**, Holotype, male (slide ANHRT Pavlova & Yakovlev 2025/086); **15.** *H. hackeri* **sp. n.**, Holotype, male (slide Prozorov 2025 1627); **16.** *H. tessellata*, female, Südafrika, Mpumalanga, 50 km NNW Nelspruit, Umg. Hazyview (CGM); **17.** *H. hillwoodi* **sp. n.**, female, Zambia, 10 km sud Muyombe (CGM).

Figure 18. Distribution map of the species of the genus *Hermannstaudeilla* gen. n.

Discussion

The genus *Salagena* currently comprises approximately 30 species (De Prins and De Prins 2025; Lehmann 2019). Recent analyses indicate that the current concept of the genus is polyphyletic and therefore requires taxonomic revision. Preliminary estimates suggest that *Salagena* includes at least four distinct genera, the descriptions of which are in preparation (Yakovlev et al., in prep.).

Representatives of the newly delimited genus *Hermannstaudeilla* are widely distributed in eastern, south-central, and southern Africa, with confirmed records from Ethiopia to the Republic of South Africa.

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